

Transverse Sound II: Critical Evaluation

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Dedicated to my grandson Akaalbir, whose curiosity and sense of wonder I share

Abstract

In the accompanying first part of the paper (Benipal 2026), Sub-Elasticity Theory is presented along with new theories of gases and liquids modelled as distinct sub-elastic materials. Using the newly formulated sub-elastic wave theory, expressions for speeds of longitudinal and transverse sound waves are derived. In this second part of the paper, the proposed theories of gas mechanics, liquid mechanics, and acoustics are critically evaluated. First, the creative steps involved in new formulations of equations of state for gases and liquids, rate-type constitutive equations, Cauchy-like dynamical equations of motion, Navier-like kinetic equations of motion involving jerk, and hyperbolic wave equations stated in terms of velocity vector field are identified. New concepts include material parallelpipedon as object of reference, motion-dependence of pressure, and introduction of full Cauchy stress rate tensor. Status of the classical theories like Euler's theory of inviscid fluid mechanics, Bernoulli's theorem, and Poisson's wave theory of sound is examined in the light of the proposed theory. Admissibility of existence of newly predicted transverse sound wave propagation through gases and liquids is examined from the perspectives of evidence, measurement, and auditory perception. Also, the newly proposed Sub-Elasticity Theory of materials and structures is contrasted with apparently similar continuum theory of hypoelasticity and new sub-elastic systems are identified. Author's opinions on some other related topics in fluid mechanics and acoustics are expressed. The implications of the proposed theory for foundations and applications of fluids mechanics are delineated. The issues like motivation for theory construction, methodology, testability, causality, theory change, diverse rationalities, etc., are discussed from the perspective of philosophy of science. Finally, new areas for further research in sub-elasticity, fluid mechanics, and acoustics are identified.

Keywords: Sub-elasticity theory, Euler fluid mechanics, classical wave theory of sound, transverse sound, hypoelasticity, philosophical issues

1. Introduction

Many good histories of fluid mechanics and acoustics are available (Rayleigh 1877/1945; Lamb 1910; Truesdell 1952; Truesdell and Toupin 1960; Truesdell and Noll 1965; Truesdell 1968; Darrigol 200; Darrigol, 2008; Tokaty 1971; Wirgin 2017; Brading and Stan 2024). Calero, Watson, and Ferreiro locate the pre-Euler genesis of fluid mechanics focussing in two problems: Problem of Resistance and Problem of Flow. The Problem of Resistance gave rise to D'Alembert's Paradox and Bernoulli's Theorem grew out of the Problem of Flow (Calero, Watson, and Ferreiro 2008; Calero 2018). However, the famous treatises on continuum mechanics (Truesdell and Toupin 1960; Truesdell and Noll 1965) have been criticized for erroneous presentation (Romano and Barretta 2025).

To recapitulate from the accompanying first part of the paper (Benipal 2026), the current state of classical fields of fluid mechanics and acoustics is summarized here: Using Laplace thermodynamic general formula for speed of sound (1816), the established formulae for speed of sound through gases and liquids were developed. Poisson (1820) developed his wave theory of longitudinal sound propagation using Euler's theory (1755) of inviscid fluids (Tokaty 1971; Wirgin 2017). Following Poisson, diverse hyperbolic wave equations are formulated later in terms of scalar velocity potential, pressure, density fields, etc., (Rayleigh 1877/1945; Lamb 1910; Feynman 1963; Truesdell and Rajagopal 2000; Herrin 2012; Jog 2002).

In acoustics, the transverse sound is deemed inadmissible. The theory of Newtonian fluids was developed by the mid-nineteenth century. Thereafter, the focus shifted to the technological and industrial applications of fluid mechanics and acoustics. Theories of non-Newtonian fluid mechanics were developed around World War II as part of the general revival of rational continuum mechanics. The wave theory of sound as well as many theories of viscous fluids are based upon Euler's formulation. However, during the last few decades, Euler's theory has been criticized from different perspectives by Birkhoff, Brenner, Ivanov and Ivanova, Liu and Liu, Kirtskhalia, Taha, Gonzales, and Shorbagy, and new theories of fluid mechanics and acoustics are proposed (Birkhoff 1950; Brenner 2003; Ivanov and Ivanova 2015; Liu and Liu 2021; Kirtskhalia 2022; Taha, Gonzales, and Shorbagy 2023).

In the first part of the paper (Benipal 2026), sub-elastic wave theory of sound is presented. Contrary to expectations, proving the existence of transverse sound waves is not the real objective of this investigation. It is motivated by the intention to understand the mechanical behavior of gases and liquids as distinct sub-elastic states of matter. This motivation itself has its origins in the Cable-Liquid Analogy identified by the author after his research into theory of sagging elastic cables (Kumar, Ganguli, and Benipal 2016). Rectangular parallelepipedon is selected as the object of reference for describing the notion of change of natural configuration upon force variations.

The choice of rectangular parallelepipedon as the material body under normal compressive forces constitutes the first mark of physical creativity in this investigation. Further mathematical derivations are borrowed from the established disciplines of continuum mechanics and structural dynamics. It must be kept in mind that while wave theory of sound pertains to sound propagation, the generation as well as reception of sound belongs to structural

dynamics dealing with vibrations of structures. In fact, the discipline of MDOF structural dynamics itself has its origins Rayleigh's treatise on sound (Rayleigh 1877/1945).

As the research investigation proceeded, new equations of state, constitutive equations, and dynamical and kinematical equations of motion got developed. From the hyperbolic wave equations stated in terms of kinematic velocity vector field, distinct expressions for the speeds of longitudinal/irrotational and transverse/equivoluminal sound waves through gases and liquids are derived. The proposed sub-elastic wave theory of sound is constructed without reference to Laplace thermodynamics-based formula for speed of sound, continuity equation, and concepts of acoustic pressure and condensation. Prediction of 'unheard and unheard of, and so inadmissible' transverse sound turned out to be a pleasant surprise.

Like other new rational theories, the theory proposed here is based upon new concepts and hypotheses from which new theorems are obtained by mathematical deduction. Admissibility of the new concepts, consistency of the new hypotheses, and correctness of mathematical deduction need to be justified by physical and logical arguments. Also, the problem of acceptability of a theory making both correct and inadmissible predictions is addressed. The foundational and philosophical implications of the proposed quite disruptive theory and possible existence of transverse waves are discussed in this second part of the paper.

2. Creation of New Theory

New fluid mechanics and acoustics concepts and hypotheses introduced in the present paper include finite-size rectangular parallelepipedon as body of reference, full rate-of-(Cauchy) stress-tensor, motion-dependent pressure, Cauchy-like equation of motion, rate-type constitutive equations, Navier-like equations of motion involving jerk, and propagation of transverse sound. The well-known Boyle-Laplace equations of state for gases are assumed to be valid, and liquids at rest are assumed to be linear elastic under pressure. Each step in mathematical deduction involves some new implicit hypotheses. The proposed theory is constructed by some bold leaps of creative imagination which is a euphemism for broken chains of logical arguments. Some preliminary mathematical and physical arguments for explanation and justification of new concepts, hypotheses, and mathematical deduction are presented in the preceding part of the paper (Benipal 2026). The steps in derivation needing rigorous mathematical justification consistent with principles of classical rational mechanics are explicitly identified below:

(a) Gases and liquids as sub-elastic states of matter lack unique natural configuration. The density-based equations of state for gases and liquids pertain to a material point and so cannot incorporate the concept of configuration. The dimensions of the material bodies define their unique equilibrium state configuration. The applied force-dimension relations for the rectangular parallelepipedon constitute new equivalent body-theoretic equations of state.

(b) From these total force-dimension relations, body theoretic rate-type equations of state are derived in terms of loading rates and velocities. In the normalized form, these equations of state for isothermal gases and elastically undeformable liquids are universal and so valid separately

for all gases and liquids. The newly formulated universal matrices have universal eigenvalues and eigenvectors.

(c) From these body-theoretic equations, point theoretic rate-type equations of state or constitutive equations relating stress-rate and rate of stretching tensors are derived in reference to principal as well as general coordinate systems. Here, stress rate tensor components are linear isotropic tensor functions of rate of instantaneous rate-of-stretching tensor components and vice versa.

(d) Classical fluid mechanics is premised upon the hypothesis that inviscid fluids, whether in a state of rest or motion, can sustain only the pressure field as the stress field. Here, this hypothesis remains valid only for fluids at rest. However, the inviscid gases and liquids in motion are assumed to support full Cauchy stress rate tensor including deviatoric stress rates, shear stress rates, and normal tensile stress rates.

(e) Further, Cauchy equations of motion are recast into rate-type dynamical equations of motion relating stress rates and jerk.

(f) Using analogy with constitutive equations of linear elasticity, coefficients in the rate-type constitutive equations corresponding to Lamé's constants are identified. Following the lead of theory of elasticity, Navier-like kinetic equations of motion stated in terms of velocity field only are deduced from the above rate-type constitutive equations and Cauchy-like dynamical equations of motion. These kinetic equations of motion include terms involving second order spatial and temporal derivatives of the velocity vector field.

(g) Thereafter, hyperbolic wave equations for sub-elastic irrotational and equivoluminal waves are obtained. Different formulae for the speed of propagation of irrotational and equivoluminal body waves are established both for gases and liquids.

The baroque theory presented here is expected to have quite high provocation potential by predicting acceptable speeds of longitudinal sound waves along with unknown transverse sound waves. In the hands of more competent acousticians, this raw theory may be developed into a mature consistent formal theory of sound. More rigorous justification needs to be offered for the claim that the general velocity field introduces only change in pressure while the deviatoric state of stress always vanishes. This is so despite the non-vanishing components of full stress rate tensor. Another promising entry point is identified as the replacement of finite-size material body assumed here for capturing the configuration change by an infinitesimally small differential body element.

It is argued by Cantrell that the radiation pressure in fluids depends upon whether the motion of the fluids normal to the direction of wave propagation is allowed, i. e., whether the acoustic beam is laterally confined or laterally unconfined (Cantrell 2018). In the present paper, the lateral motion is absent in the case of isothermal flow of gases, while it is present in the case of liquids and adiabatic flow of gases.

3. Classical Fluid Mechanics Revisited

Classical Fluid Mechanics: Serrin, and Truesdell and Toupin have provided an excellent introduction to classical fluid mechanics (Serrin 1959; Truesdell and Toupin 1960). During the mid-twentieth century renaissance of ‘rational continuum mechanics’, Truesdell School researchers (Benipal 1997) focussed on the axiomatization of exact and complete continuum theories of materials superseding the earlier approximate linear field theories (Truesdell 1952; Truesdell and Noll 1965). The non-Newtonian fluids were shown to exhibit normal stress effects which the Navier-Stokes theory could not predict. Examples of rational objective theories of fluids include Rivlin-Reiner theory, Noll’s theory of simple fluids, and Rivlin-Ericksen formulation of materials of differential type. Malvern has written a readable introduction to rational theories of fluid mechanics (Malvern 1969). However, even during this revolution no attempt was made to scrutinize the Eulerian theory of inviscid fluids which provided the foundation for all later theories of viscous fluids.

Status of Thermodynamic Equations of State: Conventional wave theories of arial sound are based upon the point-theoretic Laplace adiabatic equation of state $p = D\rho^\gamma$ for obtaining bulk modulus. Instead, the present theory invokes its body-theoretic barotropic version $pV^\gamma = C$ for deriving the rate-type constitutive equations. It is heartening to note that Boyle’s law (1662) too is intended for gaseous bodies with definite volume. For elastic liquids also, the equation of state $p = K\varepsilon_v$ is used here in preference to common equation of state $p = K\frac{\rho-\rho_0}{\rho_0}$. The conventional equations of state can capture only change of density or volume under pressure variation but not the variability of configuration of the material body. As shown in the first part of the paper, the body configuration remains invariant only under proportional variation of the applied forces though it varies under general force variations. Thus, the conventional equations of state can capture the mechanical response of the gaseous and liquid bodies only under proportional loading.

Steady Flow Paradoxes: As per classical Navier-Stokes’ equations for Newtonian fluids, steady flow introduces mean normal stress $\pi = -p + (\lambda_v + \frac{2\mu_v}{3})D_{kk}$. Clearly, negative rate of dilatation D_{kk} results over time in infinitely high-pressure instability while positive D_{kk} may lead to the inadmissible tensile mean normal stress. Incidentally, the controversial Stokes’s hypothesis (1845) ($\lambda_v + \frac{2\mu_v}{3} = 0$) is proposed to eliminate such possibility of introduction of instability and tensile mean normal stress (Truesdell 1952). The admissibility of steady flow has also been questioned earlier by Birkhoff (Birkhoff 1950).

Principle of Determinism of Pressure: In the opinion of the present author, the development of the discipline of fluid mechanics over the centuries has been afflicted by the hypothesis of motion-independence of the fluid pressure. In the present paper, it is conceded that gases and liquids at rest can support only the state of hydrostatic pressure. However, their motion introduces Cauchy stress rate tensor components including the rate of change of pressure.

In the proposed theory of inviscid fluids, steady flow introduces rate of change of pressure as $\dot{p} = -\gamma p D_{kk}$ for gases and $\dot{p} = K D_{kk}$ for liquids. Here also, negative D_{kk} causes pressure instability for both gases and liquids. However, positive D_{kk} doesn’t result in ‘tensile pressure’

in gases while it does so in liquids. In view of this, following theorem can be inferred: Infinite-duration steady flows can only be incompressible ($D_{kk} = 0$). No such condition is imposed on short-term steady flows.

Perhaps, predicted existence of ‘tensile pressure rates and tensile stress rates’ in inviscid liquids implies tension or molecular cohesion invoked by some researchers like Hughes and Gurung to explain the siphon action (Hughes and Gurung, 2014). Further, the stress rates result in variation of pressure only but not the other stresses. Thus, the instantaneous pressure field is obtained from the known initial pressure field as $p(x_1, x_2, x_3, t) = \int_0^t \dot{p} dt + p(x_1, x_2, x_3, 0)$. Here, the initial pressure field, $p_0(x_1, x_2, x_3) = p(x_1, x_2, x_3, 0)$ is generally determined by the gravitational field, e. g., in open containers like oceans and our atmosphere. However, fluid motion can introduce pressure field even in the absence of gravitational field.

Objectivity of Proposed Stress Rate Tensor: According to Noll’s Principle of Material Frame Indifference (PMFI), the stress rate used in the hypoelastic rate-type constitutive equation must also be objective (Malvern 1969; Jog 2002). In this paper, the instantaneous pressure represents an isotropic state of stress: $\sigma_{ij} = -p\delta_{ij}$. The Zaremba-Jaumann objective stress rate is given by $\tilde{\sigma} = \dot{\sigma} + \sigma W - W\sigma$ where $\dot{\sigma}$ represents Cauchy stress rate. The expression $\sigma = -pI$ implies that $\sigma W - W\sigma = 0$ and so $\dot{\sigma} = \tilde{\sigma}$. Thus, the Cauchy stress rate tensor appearing in the proposed rate-type constitutive equations is indeed objective.

Status of Continuity Equation: Craik has traced the history of formulation of continuity equation in fluid mechanics (Craik 2012). Belevich has summarized various attempts to modify the continuity equation for fluids by incorporating mass transfer caused by thermal and concentration gradients. He has also provided an example demonstrating the invalidity of the conventional continuity equation in the presence of pressure, density and temperature fields. A new continuity equation is proposed by adding a term containing density gradients (Belevich 2009).

To recapitulate, wave theories of sound employ the linearised continuity equation asserting the principle of conservation of mass during flow. In contrast, the derivations presented here are carried out without invoking the continuity equation. This role is assigned here to the rate-type versions of the equations of state and constitutive equations. Obviously, the status of continuity equation in fluid mechanics needs to be examined afresh, a need felt also by Brenner (Brenner 2003), Belevich (Belevich 2009), and Ivanov and Ivanova (Ivanov and Ivanova 2015).

Status of Euler’s Equation of Motion: The rate-type version of Cauchy’s dynamical equations of motion in place of Euler’s dynamical equation of motion is adopted in the present paper. These governing equations of motion are stated in terms of normal and shear stress rates, and rate of acceleration *aka* jerk. It is expected that on integration these equations yield Euler’s equations of motion stated in terms of total pressure and acceleration. This demands that stress rate tensor must yield on integration the state of stress represented only by the pressure. Some arguments for this eventuality are offered in the first part of the paper.

Anyway, the proposed dynamical equations of motion do yield correct predictions of speed of longitudinal waves both in gases and liquids. Euler’s equations too represent total dynamical

equations compatible with Newton's laws of motion. Thus, the proposed equations seem to augment Euler's dynamical equations of motion.

De-Unification of Fluid Mechanics: Unification of scientific theories of diverse phenomena is generally considered to be a positive development. Based on the unifying concept of pressure, Euler's dynamical equations of motion are intended for all fluids. This unification captures some similarities between gases and liquids as fluent states of matter but has resulted in obliterating some other essential distinctions between these materials. Specifically, the gaseous fluids and liquid fluids obey utterly different equations of state. This is why Navier-like kinetic equations of motion incorporating these different equations of state derived here distinguish between gases and liquids. Here, distinct theories of gas mechanics and liquid mechanics are constructed thus achieving the desired de-unification of fluid mechanics.

BCs and ICs in the BVPs and IVPs: While solving boundary/initial value problems in fluid mechanics, currently the motion-independent pressure field is assigned as an external field like the gravitational field. The boundary and initial conditions involving pressure are specified independently of those for the velocity field. As per the theory of partial differential equations, only Navier-type kinetic equations of motion derived in the present paper can yield appropriate boundary and initial conditions involving only the velocity field. These equations of motion for both gases and liquids involve second spatial and temporal derivatives of the velocity vector field. In view of this, both velocity and velocity gradient need be specified as boundary conditions. Similarly, both initial velocity and acceleration fields must be specified over the whole domain.

Isothermal Principle of Equivalence: To recapitulate, the Navier-like equation of motion for isothermal gases is stated as $-\frac{p}{2} \frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{p}{2} \nabla^2 v_i + \dot{b}_i = \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$. The isothermal equation of state for the gases is stated as $p = \rho RT$. Here, rates of change of the surface traction force $-\frac{\rho RT}{2} \left(\frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} + \nabla^2 v_i \right)$, gravitational body force $\dot{b}_i = \rho \dot{g}_i$, and inertial force $\rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$ per unit volume are all proportional to the same material density. Thus, there is an equivalence among the mass density measures determining rates of change of the gravitational, inertial and gas pressure forces. This formulation is compatible with the well-known fact that, in the gaseous bodies at rest the gravitational and the density fields determine each other through the concept of pressure field.

In view of this, an extended version of the Principle of Equivalence discovered earlier by Newton and later exploited by Einstein is established for gases obeying isothermal equation of state. For such gases, the kinetic equations of motion can be stated as $-\frac{RT}{2} \left(\frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} + \nabla^2 v_i \right) + \dot{g}_i = \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$. This equation relates the temperature and gravitational fields with the velocity field in the free space without explicit reference to density field. This jerk equation can also be stated equivalently as the universal equation $c_2^2 \left(\frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} + \nabla^2 v_i \right) + \dot{g}_i = \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$ stated in terms of definite speed of sub-elastic transverse waves. Here, the term \dot{g}_i at any point is determined by the global velocity field. So, this non-local term must be specified independently of the local velocity

field. These kinetic equations of motion for isothermal gases resemble Kepler's equations of planetary motion (1609) and Galileo's equations of motion of objects in the uniform gravitational field (1638) stated without reference to mass of moving bodies.

From the perspective of natural philosophy, all wave equations, including the above wave equation, can be interpreted as relating the categories of space and time in any field with specified transverse wave speed.

Gauss' Law for Gravitational Field: Further, Gauss' divergence theorem for the gravitational field relating the gravitational field vector with the density field is stated as $div g = \nabla \cdot g = -4\pi G\rho$. It must be appreciated that presence of gravitational and density fields also causes stress/pressure and velocity fields. These relations are stated as per Euler dynamical equations of motion $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \rho g_i = \rho \frac{Dv_i}{Dt}$ where $\frac{Dv_i}{Dt} = \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial t} + v_1 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_1} + v_2 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_2} + v_3 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_3}$ and Cauchy's dynamical of motion $\frac{\partial \sigma_{ji}}{\partial x_j} + \rho g_i = \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$. In the present paper, a rate-type dynamical equation of motion $\frac{\partial \sigma_{ji}}{\partial x_j} + \rho \dot{g}_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\rho \frac{D(v_i)}{Dt} \right)$ relating gravitational, stress, and velocity fields is adopted for fluent material field.

For a self-gravitating fluid body at rest, Euler equation (1755) and Gauss' divergence theorem (1835) are stated as $\nabla p + \rho g = 0$ and $\nabla \cdot g = -4\pi G\rho$. By eliminating g from these equations, one obtains the following equation: $\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla p}{\rho} \right) = 4\pi G\rho$ whatever its interpretation and implications. For incompressible liquids, this equation reduces to Laplacian of scalar pressure field: $\nabla \cdot (\nabla p) = \nabla^2 p = 4\pi G\rho^2$.

Measurement and Causality in Fluid Mechanics: As per the above new equations of state, the configuration of the gaseous and liquid bodies is determined by the relative magnitudes of applied forces. This holds even when these forces happen to be too small to be sensed and measured by using current techniques. This can happen in the presence of very low gravitational field. In such cases, the configuration-determining forces are practically indeterminate, and so the concept of causality in this sense becomes meaningless in fluid mechanics.

Criticism of Navier-Stokes Equations: The Stokes Hypothesis incorporated in the standard version of the Navier-Stokes Equations does not imply incompressibility. As such, the Stokes Hypothesis is incompatible with continuity equation asserting the conservation of mass (Caltagirone 2021).

According to Sheng, the classical assumption of symmetric viscous stress tensor conflicts with the solution of Couette flow. A more realistic friction asymmetric viscous stress tensor is proposed by him which is determined as a linear function of asymmetric velocity gradient tensor L in place of symmetric rate of stretching tensor D . Navier-Stokes equations are retrieved for incompressible flow while a different assumption like Stokes Condition (1845) is required for compressible flows (Sheng 2020). Natarajan and Natarajan are not convinced by the introduction of asymmetric stress tensor proposed by Sheng for non-polar fluids. The so-called 'friction asymmetric viscous stress tensor' is interpreted by them as non-isotropic part of

vorticity-induced viscous stress tensor. Navier-Stokes Equations are retrieved, as claimed, fortuitously only for chosen rectangular coordinate system, but not in other coordinate systems (Natarajan and Natarajan 2021).

Sub-Elastic Configurational Energy: To recapitulate from part I (Benipal 2026), the forces $P_i(a_1, a_2, a_3) = a_i^{-(3\gamma-2)} f\left(\frac{a_j}{a_i}, \frac{a_k}{a_i}\right)$ acting on the gaseous rectangular parallelepipedon are functions homogeneous of the order $-(3\gamma - 2)$ of its dimensions (a_1, a_2, a_3) . Thus, the configurational energy $W(a_1, a_2, a_3)$ turns out to be $-3(\gamma - 1)$ order homogeneous function such that the following relation applies: $\frac{\partial W}{\partial a_r} a_r = P_r a_r = -3(\gamma - 1)W$. One obtains the expression for the configurational strain energy as $W = \frac{-1}{3(\gamma-1)} (P_1 a_1 + P_2 a_2 + P_3 a_3)$. Or equivalently, $W = \frac{-C}{(\gamma-1)V^{\gamma-1}}$. Indeed, the gaseous body turns out to be a conservative system as $\frac{\partial W}{\partial a_r} = P_r$. Clearly, these expressions hold only when $\gamma \neq 1$. For incompressible liquids, the body dimensions are zero order homogeneous functions of the applied forces. However, the applied forces are not uniquely determined by the body dimensions. As a matter of fact, the same body dimensions correspond to an infinite set of proportional applied forces. So, the energy function $W(a_1, a_2, a_3)$ cannot be defined for liquids.

Similarly, the following expressions for the adiabatic gaseous body dimensions as functions of the applied forces are established: $a_1 = P_1^{\frac{-1}{(3\gamma-2)}} C \left[\frac{P_2 P_3}{P_1 P_1} \right]^{\gamma-1}$, $a_2 = P_2^{\frac{-1}{(3\gamma-2)}} C \left[\frac{P_3 P_1}{P_2 P_2} \right]^{\gamma-1}$, and $a_3 = P_3^{\frac{-1}{(3\gamma-2)}} C \left[\frac{P_1 P_2}{P_3 P_3} \right]^{\gamma-1}$. The symmetric tangent flexibility matrix is obtained as $f_{ij} = \frac{\partial a_i}{\partial P_j} = \frac{-(3\gamma-2)\delta_{ij} + (\gamma-1)\frac{a_i}{P_j}}{(3\gamma-2)}$. Here, the body dimensions are $\frac{-1}{(3\gamma-2)}$ order homogeneous function of equilibrated forces. The configurational complementary energy $\Omega(P_1, P_2, P_3)$ turns out to be (one order higher), i. e., $\frac{3(\gamma-1)}{(3\gamma-2)}$ order homogeneous function of these forces. Euler's theorem for homogeneous functions yields $\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial P_r} P_r = \frac{3(\gamma-1)}{(3\gamma-2)} \Omega$. As configurational complementary energy plays the role of potential function for the conservative system, $\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial P_r} = a_r$, the following expression is derived: $\Omega(P_1, P_2, P_3) = \frac{3\gamma-2}{3(\gamma-1)} (P_1 a_1 + P_2 a_2 + P_3 a_3)$. This implies that the configurational complementary energy for the special case of isothermal gas flows ($\gamma = 1$) turns out to be infinitely large. It has been verified that $\Omega(P_1, P_2, P_3) + W(a_1, a_2, a_3) = P_1 a_1 + P_2 a_2 + P_3 a_3$ for adiabatic flows of gases.

Similarly, dimensions of the conservative incompressible liquid body are functions homogeneous of order zero of the applied forces. Consequently, configurational complementary energy is first order homogeneous function of the forces. Thus, $\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial P_r} P_r = \Omega = P_1 a_1 + P_2 a_2 + P_3 a_3$. The configuration-dependent sub-elastic complementary energy, called configurational complementary energy, is distinct from the elastic complementary energy. For elastic liquids, the elastic complementary energy is given by $U = \frac{1}{2} \frac{p^2}{K}$ per unit volume. In contrast, the gases exhibit purely configurational behaviour sans elastic complementary energy.

For the gaseous and liquid bodies, the equality $P_1 a_1 = P_2 a_2 = P_3 a_3 = pV$ holds. In view of this, configurational complementary energy is expressed as $\Omega(P_1, P_2, P_3) = \frac{3\gamma-2}{\gamma-1} pV$. Equivalently, $\Omega(p) = \frac{3\gamma-2}{\gamma-1} p$ represents their configurational complementary energy density. Obviously, this density is infinitely large for the special case of isothermal gases. Similarly, for incompressible liquids, one obtains the expression $\Omega(P_1, P_2, P_3) = 3pV$. This yields the configurational complementary energy density as $\Omega(P_1, P_2, P_3) = 3p$.

Bernoulli's Theorem: Bernoulli's theorem in hydrodynamics and aerodynamics was first enunciated by Daniel Bernoulli (1738) expressing the principle of conservation of energy for fluids along streamlines. Generally, it is stated for incompressible flows along a streamline as $p + \Psi + \frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 = \text{Constant}$ where Ψ denotes the gravitational potential. Daniel Bernoulli is credited (Oliveira 2019) with distinguishing between static pressure p and dynamic pressure $q = p + \frac{1}{2}\rho v^2$. Daniel Bernoulli also identified the difference between *potential ascent* and *actual descent* corresponding to kinetic energy and potential energy respectively (Tou 2019).

Its explicit derivation in its current form is credited to Euler (1752). Euler's general version of Bernoulli's theorem for compressible flows along a streamline is stated as $\int \frac{dp}{\rho} + \frac{\Psi}{\rho} + \frac{1}{2}v^2 = \text{Constant}$. For special cases, Bernoulli's theorem attains the following forms:

Isentropic flows (Jog 2002): $\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1} p + \Psi + \frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 = \text{Constant}$ for $\gamma > 1$

Isothermal flows: $p \log p + \Psi + \frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 = \text{Constant}$

Thus, this common consensus formulation does not explicitly clarify validity of the theorem for different inviscid gases and liquids. It seems that Bernoulli's equation $p + \Psi + \frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 = \text{Constant}$ applies only to inherently incompressible liquids ignoring their elastic energy component. Furthermore, Euler's expression $\int \frac{dp}{\rho} + \frac{\Psi}{\rho} + \frac{1}{2}v^2 = \text{Constant}$ is valid for gases. Bernoulli's original theorem for incompressible fluids is generally derived from the momentum equation represented by Euler's equation of motion. Such is the case even though Euler's equation of motion is valid for both incompressible and compressible fluids. A slightly more general form valid for incompressible and compressible fluids is derived by Jog (Jog 2002) from the energy equation.

Principle of conservation of energy implies temporal invariance of total energy density for closed systems. In contrast, Bernoulli's theorem asserts the spatial invariance of total energy density along a streamline. In all these versions of the Bernoulli's theorem, the first term plays the role of energy density corresponding to elastic strain energy in solids. To recapitulate, Euler's equation of motion for inviscid fluids is stated as $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \rho g_i = \rho \frac{Dv_i}{Dt}$. Curiously, here the pressure gradient yields traction force per unit volume. It is conjectured here that the pressure field $p(x_1, x_2, x_3)$ is being treated as energy potential at par with gravitational potential whose spatial gradient yields gravitational force per unit volume. In this sense, Cauchy's stress tensor

plays a similar role of potential energy in Cauchy's equations of motion applicable to both the elastic solids and the viscous fluids.

Different expressions for the sub-elastic configurational energy are derived above for gases and liquids. It can be observed that these expressions for configurational energy density differ from the corresponding energy terms appearing in the Bernoulli's theorem. Further, the energy potential in Euler's equation of motion is different from both these configurational energy potentials. Thus, there is a need to reconcile these observed incompatibilities among potentials. Also, for closure of the fluid theory, Bernoulli's theorem for compressible fluids must also be deduced from Euler's equation of motion. As energy function can be defined for them, sub-elastic homogeneous mechanical systems are always conservative.

Liquid Flow Vs. Fall Conjecture: Both the Bernoulli's theorem and Euler's equations of motion treat pressure potential p at par with the gravitational potential Ψ . To be specific, Bernoulli's theorem demands that the sum $p + \Psi$ remain spatially invariant along a streamline with uniform velocity. According to Euler's equations of motion, their spatial gradient along any direction yields force per unit volume in that direction. In a uniform steady velocity field with nil total acceleration $\frac{Dv_i}{Dt}$, the sum $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial x_i}$ vanishes as $b_i = \rho g_i = \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial x_i}$. Equivalently stated, one obtains, $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial x_i}$. As $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i}$ exceeds $(-\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial x_i})$, the fluid gets accelerated in the corresponding direction. The fluid gets accelerated along a direction of negative pressure gradient. In the limiting case, $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i}$ approaches zero from negative side and the acceleration is caused solely by the gravitational forces. The pressure gradient $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i}$ cannot assume positive values.

In view of these arguments, it is conjectured here that, in the presence of gravitational field, the liquid flow acceleration at a point cannot exceed gravitational acceleration. When the liquid acceleration reaches this limiting value, the flow ceases, and the liquid starts to fall. This implies that only the pressure gradient opposing the gravitational field affects the flow. Otherwise, the pressure gradient does not operate. This contention is compatible with the fact that, in a state of rest, the force associated with pressure gradient opposes the gravitational force. Inviscid liquid flow is governed by Euler partial differential equation of motion, while the fall is governed by Newton's algebraic equations of motion.

In his analysis of Galileo's classic two-bucket experiment (1638), Bistafa assumes that the water discharging from the upper bucket falls freely under gravitational force and vanishing pressure gradient (Bistafa 2018). As the acceleration nowhere exceeds the constant acceleration due to gravity, the analysis does not contradict the author's above conjecture. The concept of convective acceleration does not seem to be valid for liquids falling at gravitational acceleration. It is not clear whether sound propagation occurs through falling liquid jets.

It is conjectured here that the liquid does not flow but falls through the descending branch of the siphon. Perhaps, neglecting this distinction between liquid flow and fall has obstructed the development of satisfactory theory explaining the siphon action.

Classical Efflux Problem Revisited: Consider the steady flow of an incompressible inviscid liquid through prismatic horizontal tube subjected to constant but different pressures at its ends ($p_1 > p_2$). The tube-end pressures can be maintained by two liquid containers with top water surfaces held at different levels. This classical problem has been chosen as the reference problem by Daniel Bernoulli (1738), Johann Bernoulli (1742), D'Alembert (1744), and later by Euler (1755) for laying the foundations of fluid dynamics in the first half of eighteenth century. A nuanced story of the engagement of these savants with this problem and its connection with paradigmatic compound pendulum motion has been retold by Darrigol and Frisch (Darrigol and Frisch 2008).

The principle of conservation of mass *aka* the continuity equation implies uniform velocity along the horizontal direction. In view of vertical direction of gravitational force, the gravitational potential remains constant along the tube. Bernoulli's theorem implies uniform pressure field along the tube length. Thus, both the pressure gradient and the velocity gradient vanish along the tube. No gravitational force acts along the tube. The flow through the tube being steady, the velocity at all sections remains constant and does not vary with time. Thus, Euler's equation of fluid motion is vacuously satisfied. No net force acts of the liquid body contained with the tube. According to Newton's first law of motion, the liquid body continues to move at a constant velocity through the tube.

However, in this thought experiment, a question naturally arises: How can the pressure field be uniform along the tube subjected to different pressures at its ends? Why doesn't the net force ($p_1 - p_2$) A acting on the liquid in the tube cause any acceleration? What are the magnitudes of uniform pressure and the uniform velocity along the tube? These questions pertaining to the simplest possible flow problem are not directly confronted in modern textbooks. In the modern presentations of Bernoulli's problem, these questions are masked by the focus on additional complexities associated with variability of tube area and/or elevation along its length as well as with unsteady and compressible flows of viscous fluids. The implicit answers to these questions have been provided by Daniel Bernoulli (1738). In the reference figure of the efflux problem, Daniel Bernoulli shows the pressure to be same at all sections of the tube. It is merely implied that the pressure at all sections of the tube equals the lower applied end pressure (Darrigol and Frisch 2008).

Here, it is conjectured that the uniform pressure in the length segment ($0_+ < x \leq L$) of the tube equals the lower end-pressure $p(x) = p_2$. There is a discontinuity of pressure and velocity at the section $x = 0$, with pressure p_1 and velocity $V_1 = 0$ at $x = 0_-$ and pressure p_2 and velocity $V_2 = V$ at $x = 0_+$. In place of such a discontinuity at a section, perhaps the pressure and velocity gradients are confined to a very small segment of finite length s near the higher-pressure end. In that small region, the pressure varies from higher to lower pressure and velocity increases from zero to V . The net force causes the liquid body in this segment to move as a rigid body.

Here, the arguments from Variable Mass Dynamics dealing with motion of bodies with time-dependent mass (Pesce and Casetta 2007) are being invoked. The theory of Variable Mass Dynamics yielded the well-known Rocket Equation. Here, the analysis is based upon the

velocities of the mass joining and/or leaving the body relative to its velocity. To recapitulate, Newton's second law of motion as well as the principle of balance of linear momentum valid only for constant mass are not applicable in this case. It must be kept in mind that Newton's laws of motion apply to material bodies with impenetrable bounding surface.

In the present thought experiment, the total mass of the liquid in tube is assumed to remain mathematically invariant in time ($\dot{M} = 0$) though ontologically it is not the same mass all the time. This is because of the fact the rate of mass \dot{M}_1 joining the liquid body at the higher-pressure end equals the rate of mass \dot{M}_2 exiting at the lower-pressure end thus resulting in $\dot{M} = \dot{M}_1 + \dot{M}_2 = 0$. It is considered that liquid at rest at $x = 0_-$ joins the body while the liquid leaving at $x = s$ has the same velocity as that of the liquid body. The liquid leaving this region leaves at nil relative velocity and so does not affect the linear momentum of the body. The total linear momentum transferred by the net force equals that acquired by the joining liquid mass when, starting from rest, it acquires definite velocity V_2 in the small length segment.

The rate of increase of linear momentum of the body associated with inflow is caused by the net force. The rate of mass flowing through the tube is given as $\dot{M}_1 = \rho AV_2$, while the rate of linear momentum acquired by the mass entering at $x = 0$ is obtained as $\dot{M}_1(V_2 - V_1) = \rho AV_2(V_2 - V_1)$. The net force $F = (p_1 - p_2) A$ is acting on the mass in the small segment. Knowing that the rate of change of linear momentum equals applied net force, one obtains the equation: $(p_1 - p_2) A = \rho AV_2(V_2 - V_1)$. Some algebraic manipulation yields $\frac{p_1 - p_2}{s} = \rho \frac{V_2 - V_1}{s} V$. In terms of the infinitesimally small length segment $s \approx dx$, following expressions for pressure and velocity gradients are derived: $\frac{p_1 - p_2}{s} = \frac{dp}{dx}$ and $\frac{V_2 - V_1}{s} = \frac{dV}{dx}$. Thus, the above algebraic equation can be transformed into the familiar one-dimensional Euler's differential equation of fluid motion in terms of pressure and velocity gradients stated as follows: $\frac{dp}{dx} = \rho \frac{dV}{dx} V$.

Here, the convective part of the acceleration $\frac{dV}{dx} V$ is deduced from Variable Mass Dynamics Theory of Fluid Flow. It must be acknowledged that the concept of convective acceleration appearing in Euler's later equations of fluid motion (1755) was first introduced by Johann Bernoulli (1742) while investigating the efflux problem being discussed here (Darrigol and Frisch 2008). The possible connection between Johann Bernoulli's convective acceleration of fluids, the control volume concept, and some continuum-theoretic version of Variable Mass Dynamics needs to be explored.

This Variable Mass Dynamics theory of efflux may also help explain the siphon action.

A Physical Theory of Parameter Variation: In the familiar expressions representing Newton's second law of motion $F = Ma$ and Hooke's law $F = Ku$, the temporal variation of force is connected to the corresponding variation of acceleration a and elastic displacement u , viz., $F(t) = Ma(t)$ and $F(t) = Ku(t)$. Here, the physical parameters M and K are assumed to be constant. The same purely mathematical approach cannot incorporate the autonomous temporal variation of parameters $M(t)$ and $K(t)$ as the equalities $F(t) = M(t)a(t)$, $F = M\dot{V} + \dot{M}V$,

and $F(t) = K(t)u(t)$ are invalid. Thus, a physical mechanism for incorporating the temporal autonomous variation of parameters must be developed.

The present author has developed Dissolution-Precipitation Mechanism and Theory for uniaxial state of stress (Benipal 1995) and it was generalized later (Suter and Benipal 2010)) to explain the observed creep of reacting elastic solids like concrete. The stiffness of a reacting solid body decreases by dissolution of reacting elastic phase and increases by precipitation of elastic reaction products. The transformation of the stressed elastic phase upon dissolution into stress-free solute causes time-dependent increase in elastic displacements (identified as creep) under sustained load. Whether the stiffness increases, decreases, or even remains constant, the Dissolution-Precipitation Mechanism causes creep-like mechanical response.

An attempt has been made by the author to construct a preliminary physical theory of parameter variation (Benipal 2025). It is shown that both Variable Mass Dynamics and Variable Material Stiffness are instances of autonomous temporal variation of system parameters. Now, fluid flow through tubes seems to constitute another example of Variable Mass Dynamics.

The above discussion raises doubts regarding the direct unscrutinized validity of the theory of linear differential equations like $s_2(x)y(x)'' + s_1(x)y(x)' + s_0(x)y(x) = h(x)$ with variable parameters s_i to physical systems. This has very unsettling implications for the relationship between mathematics and physics in theoretical physics.

4. Sub-Elastic Wave Theory and Transverse Sound

Sub-Elastic Wave Theory: The proposed theory of sound is premised upon the reformulated body-theoretic equations of state, new constitutive equations, rate-type dynamical and kinetic equations of motion, and hyperbolic wave equations. Hyperbolic wave equations stated in terms of velocity vector field are derived for irrotational and equivoluminal waves predicting speeds of their propagation through gases and liquids. Conventional concepts like acoustic pressure and condensation, the continuity equation, and Laplace thermodynamic formula $c = \sqrt{dp/d\rho}$ are not invoked in the derivation. Both the kinetic equations of motion and hyperbolic wave equations contain second order spatial and temporal partial derivatives of the velocity field. The second temporal derivative of the velocity field implies rate of acceleration *aka* jerk. As expected, this is compatible with the third order governing differential equation of motion for vibrating sagging elasto-flexible cables (Kumar, Ganguli, and Benipal 2016).

These sub-elastic waves are shown to be perturbations in the ambient velocity field. As sound waves travel relative to the ambient flow, their absolute speed is affected by the flow velocity, e. g., wind or current velocity. Speed of sound is known to be independent of the speed of its source as well as the motion of the medium of its propagation (Cheng and Read 2021). Only temporally varying gravitational fields are predicted to affect the speed of sound. Also, both irrotational and equivoluminal wave velocities in both gases and liquids are predicted to increase with pressure.

Status of Poisson's Wave Theory: Differentiating with respect to time the adiabatic equation of state $pV^\gamma = C$ for gases yields the rate-type equation $\dot{p} = -\gamma p D_{kk}$ in view of the definition $\dot{V}/V = D_{kk}$. Inserting it in the rate-type Cauchy's dynamical equation of motion $\frac{\partial \dot{p}}{\partial x_i} = \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$, one obtains $-\gamma p \frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} = \rho \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$. As $\frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} = \nabla^2 v_i$ for irrotational flow, one arrives at the wave equation $\nabla^2 v_i = -\frac{\rho}{\gamma p} \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$ or $\nabla^2 v_i = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2}$ stated, for the first time, in terms of velocity vector field. Here, c represents the longitudinal arial wave speeds as per the Laplace formula $c = \sqrt{\frac{-\gamma p}{\rho}}$.

Similarly, the constitutive equation $p = K \varepsilon_v$ for elastic liquids yields its rate-type version $\dot{p} = K D_{kk}$ where $\varepsilon_v = D_{kk}$. Following the same line of argument, the expression for speed c of longitudinal wave through liquids is derived as $c = \sqrt{K/\rho}$. In these derivations, the rate of change of pressure is assumed to represent the stress rate tensor as $\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = -\dot{p} \delta_{ij}$ in place of the full expression $\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = \dot{\sigma}_m \delta_{ij} + \dot{s}_{ij}$ proposed in this paper. Thus, Poisson's wave theory turns out to be a special case of the proposed sub-elastic wave theory. This special case ignores the presence of the deviatoric stress rate tensor and so of the deviatoric component of the symmetric part of the velocity gradient tensor.

Equivoluminal Sound Waves: The most surprising, though unintended, contribution of the present paper is the prediction of equivoluminal/transverse waves propagating through gases and liquids. There are two transverse sound waves propagating at the same speed in two mutually orthogonal planes both containing the axis of propagation. This case is reminiscent of the mutually orthogonal electric and magnetic components of the transverse electromagnetic wave travelling at the same speed of light. Such waves have not yet been detected or perceived. With no pretension of parity of stature, the situation is observed to be akin to Maxwell's Conjecture (1864) identifying light as a transverse electromagnetic wave. The existence of such waves having speed equal to the known speed of light was proved much later by Hertz (1888). As per Sengupta and Sarkar, in the intervening period nobody knew how to electromagnetically generate and detect such waves (Sengupta and Sarkar 2003).

Indirect Evidence for Transverse Sound Waves: It is well-known (Wikipedia Article on Second Sound 2024) that the speeds of first and second sounds propagating in superfluid Helium exhibiting superconductivity are related as $c_1^2 = 3c_2^2$. Curiously, the speeds of propagation of the irrotational and equivoluminal waves through adiabatic gaseous medium predicted here bear a similar numerical ratio 2.8 as $c_1^2 = 2\gamma c_2^2$ where $\gamma = 1.4$ for air. This corresponding relation for isothermal gases is $c_1^2 = 2c_2^2$.

Shear-type acoustic gravity waves with vanishing dilatation and invariant pressure and density are predicted by Godin (Godin 2014) to propagate through compressible inhomogeneous inviscid quiescent fluids in a uniform gravity field. According to Dukhin and Goetz, in contrast to compressional waves, shear and thermal waves exist only in the close vicinity of phase boundaries (Dukhin and Goetz 2002). As established separately by Bernstein and Nariboli, both irrotational and equivoluminal waves can be transmitted in a hypoelastic material with

hydrostatic state of stress (Bernstein 1962; Nariboli 1964). Similarly, two types of inhomogeneous attenuated plane waves have earlier been predicted by Scott in compressible viscous fluids: Two transverse waves without density or pressure, and a longitudinal wave without vorticity fluctuation (Scott 1995).

Evanescent wave coupling is observed to occur when the sound source is in water at a depth smaller than the acoustic wavelength. It renders the water-air interface anomalously transparent and results in increased infrasonic flux in the atmosphere. These infrasonic waves are observed to travel through stratospheric duct at a velocity of 280m/s. The multiple explanations offered for this phenomenon of anomalous transparency of the water-air interface are unsatisfactory (Godin 2008; Evers, Brown, Heaney, Assink, Smets, and Snellen 2014). It is interesting to note that the atmospheric infrasonic wave velocity of 280m/s happens to equal the transverse arial wave velocity ($c_2 = \sqrt{\frac{-p}{2\rho}}$) as predicted in the present paper. In view of this, it is conjectured that the atmospheric infrasonic wave is a transverse arial wave.

In a new formulation of Navier-Stokes Equations by Caltagirone, the existence of both longitudinal and transverse waves is predicted. However, the transverse waves are shown to suffer very rapid attenuation (Caltagirone 2021). Further, it has been observed by Ranjan that both longitudinal and transverse waves exist at the interface of viscous fluids. The longitudinal waves are caused by capillary/gravity effects while the transverse waves are caused by interfacial elasticity (Ranjan 2021). The present theory demands the formulation of new boundary conditions separately for propagation of longitudinal and transverse waves across the solid-fluid, gas-gas, liquid-liquid, and gas-liquid interfaces.

Transonic Aerodynamics: Transonic aerodynamics deals with airflow around objects moving at speeds V closer to the local speed of sound. Transonic flow is characterized by the co-existence of subsonic and supersonic regions on the object, shock waves, higher drag forces, and stability issues. The critical Mach number M_{cr} represents the minimum speed at which the flow at some point on the object reaches the Mach 1. The drag-divergence Mach number M_{dd} marks the minimum speed beyond which the aerodynamic drag increases substantially with speed of the object. Typical value of M_{dd} is 0.6 Mach or higher, but always slightly higher than M_{cr} . These numbers M_{dd} and M_{cr} are very important in the design of supersonic and hypersonic aeroplanes, space vehicles, and missiles (Tokaty 1971; Wikipedia articles on Transonic and on Drag-Divergence Mach Number).

In the present paper, the longitudinal and transverse arial sound wave speeds are given respectively as $c_1 = \sqrt{\frac{-\gamma p}{\rho}}$ and $c_2 = \sqrt{\frac{-p}{2\rho}}$. One obtains the expression $c_2 = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\gamma}} c_1$ and defining Mach number as $M = \frac{v}{c_1}$, the transverse arial sound wave speed corresponds to Mach number $M_2 = \frac{c_2}{c_1} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2\gamma}}$. As $\gamma = 1.4$ for air, $M_2 = 0.598$. Thus, $M_2 \cong M_{dd}$. This numerical coincidence prompts the following conjecture: The drag-divergence Mach number in transonic aerodynamics is strongly associated the transverse arial sound wave predicted here.

Like aerodynamic drag on a moving body, hydrodynamic drag too is proportional to its velocity at low velocities, while it increases with the square of velocity at higher velocities. Perhaps, the transition from linear to quadratic dependence of hydrodynamic drag on velocity takes place at the body velocities equal to the transverse wave speed in water. However, the transverse wave speed increases with depth of water but remains very low in comparison to longitudinal wave velocity $c_2 \cong \sqrt{\frac{p}{2K}} c_1$. Thus, quadratic dependence of drag on velocity is predominantly observed. Also, in this case, the longitudinal wave velocity being quite high, the flow is always subsonic or transonic, but never super/hypersonic. The onset of subsonic turbulence in air is also characterized by a Mach number of approximately 0.5. Subsonic turbulence possibly commences when the air flow velocity just exceeds the speed of transverse sound wave.

Flow-Induced Stiffness: To recapitulate, both the sagging cables and the fluid bodies lack any passive state stiffness. In the absence of gravitational forces, the free motion of sagging flexible cables introduces inertial and internal resistive forces which impart definite stiffness assigning definite modal frequencies to the system. It is demonstrated that when damped sagging flexible cables in a passive state are subjected to initial velocities, these systems eventually occupy a different natural state after dissipation of initial energy (Kumar and Benipal 2025). A little reflection reveals that the same conclusions apply to the liquid and gaseous bodies as well. Explicitly stated, free fluid flow can generate pressure field as $\dot{p} = BD_{kk}$ and so impart stiffness to the system. Such flow-induced stiffness is expected to render the flowing liquids and gases capable of supporting longitudinal and transverse wave propagation even in the absence of external pressure and gravitational field. Thus, a new explanation for the observed flow-induced sound is offered.

Flow-Induced Sound: In some situations, rotational kinetic energy gets converted into longitudinal vortex sound wave. Aeroacoustics deals with general noise, including vortex sound, generated by turbulence or aerodynamic forces. In the absence of any satisfactory theory, practical aeroacoustics is based on the Lighthill Aeroacoustic Analogy (1952). Here, for compressible Newtonian fluids, an inhomogeneous wave equation for density waves is derived with a source term representing Lighthill turbulence stress tensor T_{ij} stated as $\frac{\partial^2 \rho}{\partial t^2} - c^2 \nabla^2 \rho = \frac{\partial^2 T_{ij}}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}$. Later, Landau and Lifshitz (1987) derived a similar approximate wave equation $\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 p = \frac{\partial^2 (\rho v_i v_j)}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}$ for pressure of incompressible inviscid fluids wherein the Lighthill stress tensor is given by $T_{ij} = \rho v_i v_j$ (Aeroacoustics: Wikipedia).

To recapitulate, the following Navier-like equations of motion for gases and liquids respectively are derived in first part of the present paper:

$$-\left(\gamma - \frac{1}{2}\right) p \frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{p}{2} \nabla^2 v_i + \dot{b}_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\rho \frac{D(v_i)}{Dt} \right)$$

$$K \left(\frac{3K+0.5p}{3K+p} \right) \frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} - \left(\frac{1.5Kp}{3K+p} \right) \nabla^2 v_i + \dot{b}_i = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\rho \frac{D(v_i)}{Dt} \right)$$

Here, $\frac{Dv_i}{Dt} = \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial t} + v_1 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_1} + v_2 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_2} + v_3 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_3}$. In terms of irrotational and transverse wave speeds, a unified inhomogeneous wave equation for (compressible) gases and liquids is obtained as below:

$$(c_1^2 - c_2^2) \frac{\partial D_{kk}}{\partial x_i} + c_2^2 \nabla^2 v_i - \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left[\rho \left(v_1 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_1} + v_2 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_2} + v_3 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_3} \right) \right] - \dot{g}_i$$

For liquids, the density is practically constant. Thus, for liquids and incompressible flows of gases, the above equations can be restated as the following Unified inhomogeneous wave equations:

$$\text{Irrotational waves: } c_1^2 \nabla^2 v_i - \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(v_1 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_1} + v_2 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_2} + v_3 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_3} \right) - \dot{g}_i$$

$$\text{Equivoluminal waves: } c_2^2 \nabla^2 v_i - \frac{\partial^2 v_i}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(v_1 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_1} + v_2 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_2} + v_3 \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_3} \right) - \dot{g}_i$$

As in the case of above aeroacoustic analogies, the terms on the right-hand side represent the sources of flow-induced sound. Thus, the rates of variation of convective acceleration *aka* ‘convective jerk’ and gravitational field are identified as sources of irrotational and equivoluminal sound waves in flowing gases and liquids. For near-Earth laboratory, industrial and aeronautical applications, gravitational field is assumed to be constant ($\dot{g}_i = 0$), only convective jerk remains the source of two types of flow-induced sound waves.

Density-Dependence of Speed of Sound: Using the Laplace adiabatic equation of state $p = D\rho^\gamma$, one obtains the expressions for speeds of irrotational and equivoluminal sound waves in terms of density respectively as $c_1 = \sqrt{\gamma D\rho^{\gamma-1}}$ and $c_2 = \sqrt{\frac{D\rho^{\gamma-1}}{2}}$. The speed of both the irrotational and equivoluminal sound waves is predicted to increase with gas density. Thus, as per the barotropic formulation, the density field in the atmosphere determines the local speed of sound which, in turn, determines the local Mach Number. As the local speed of sound is predicted to vanish asymptotically with altitude, acoustic signals from the Earth’s surface cannot ever reach the outer most layers of its atmosphere.

It must be observed that in deriving the above speed-density relations, the minus sign in the equations $c_1 = \sqrt{\frac{-\gamma}{\rho}}$ and $c_2 = \sqrt{\frac{-p}{2\rho}}$ is dropped. This omission has its origin in the basic equations of state like $p = D\rho^\gamma$ where pressure, an isotropic negative normal stress state, is interpreted as a positive scalar quantity. Here, an increase of pressure results in an increase in density!!! This interpretation of pressure has been adopted uncritically in the present paper. However, it is at variance with the norm in continuum mechanics wherein tensile normal stresses are treated as positive. For elastic liquids, the equation $\dot{p} = KD_{kk}$ implies an absurd conclusion that an increase in pressure results in an increase in volume. This inconsistency over sign convention between the applied areas of fluid mechanics, soil mechanics and concrete mechanics, on the one hand, and general theory of continuum mechanics on the other needs to be corrected.

Boyle's Law (1642) Revisited: Since Archimedes's fluidstatics in third century BC, the notion of fluid pressure developed gradually from empirical experience. Here, the focus is on Boyle's quantitative law $pV = C$ which asserts that an increase in pressure causes decrease in volume, both pressure and volume being positive quantities. This implies that vanishing pressure corresponds to infinitely high volume and vice versa. In other words, an increase of pressure applied on a gaseous body in its passive state is not associated with the change in volume but with the volume corresponding to the applied pressure. In view of this inconsistency in Boyle's law, there seems to be a need to propose an alternative positive scalar measure q , in place of pressure p of the state of stress for gaseous bodies with volume V .

Torricelli's Theorem (1743) Revisited: According to Torricelli's Theorem (1643), the velocity V of water flowing out of a small hole located distance h below water level in a water vessel is given by $V = \sqrt{2gh}$. Knowing that pressure p in the vessel at the level of the hole equals ρgh , the above expression can be restated as $V = \sqrt{\frac{2p}{\rho}}$. The expression for the speed of transverse

sound through elastically incompressible liquids is derived in the present paper as $c_2 = \sqrt{\frac{-p}{2\rho}}$.

Comparing these expressions for V and c_2 and ignoring the sign convention, one gets the equality $V = 2c_2$. This implies that the velocity of water jet is twice the speed of transverse sound through water in the vessel at the level of the hole. The compressible gas flow velocity through a small orifice into vacuum is given by Saint Venant - Wantzel equation (1839) stated

as $V = \sqrt{\frac{2\gamma p}{\gamma-1\rho}}$. Thus, $V = c_1 \sqrt{\frac{2}{\gamma-1}} = 2c_2 \sqrt{\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1}}$.

At this juncture, it is instructive to note that Newton (1687) derived his expression for speed of arial sound ($c = \sqrt{\frac{p}{\rho}}$) from the considerations resembling those of Torricelli (1643). Newton considered the air pressure to be given by half the height of the air column.

It is well known that both the choked flow of compressible fluids and critical flow of both compressible and incompressible fluids occur when the flow velocity equals the local sonic velocity. In the case of gas flow through nozzles, the flow velocity cannot exceed the sonic speed determined by the upstream pressure resulting in choked flow. The flow velocity cannot be increased further merely by decreasing the downward pressure. Supercritical flow can occur in shallow open channels with steep slope when the flow velocity exceeds the wave speed. It seems that such supercritical condition is associated with 'falling' rather than flowing. Also, supersonic flow occurs in diverging section of the nozzle while choked flow occurs at its throat. The explanation for the rather controversial phenomenon of Sanal Flow Choking (Sanal Kumar et al 2020; Chandran, Chanda, Natarajan, and Mehta 2024) may possibly be offered by invoking the transverse sound wave predicted here. As per the proposed Sound Postulate in sonic relativity, the local speed of sound constitutes the upper limit on the flow velocity (Cheng and Read 2021).

Detection and Auditory Perception of Transverse Sound: Transverse waves have not yet been detected or perceived, apparently rendering these waves inadmissible. However, it is argued

here that such inference from experiment and experience is not inevitable. The classical theory of fluids is not equipped to predict transverse waves. All experimentation being theory-soaked, the measuring instruments are designed only to detect longitudinal waves. Perhaps, the presence of transverse waves is being treated as noise to be eliminated in more efficient design of sonic instruments.

As per Darwin's theory of evolution, marine creatures, terrestrial animals, birds, and insects have evolved in their respective ambient sonic environments. They can communicate only by making and hearing longitudinal wave sounds propagating through water and air. Perhaps the animals, including humans, are endowed with hearing only longitudinal waves. This is because hearing slower transverse sound waves also would have disrupted their sonic communication. However, lack of perception of transverse sound waves does not imply their absence in air or water. After all, even though the auditory perception is limited to the finite auditory frequency range, the sound waves of infrasonic and ultrasonic frequencies do exist. Further, there being such a variety of modes of auditory perception in the animal world (Scanes 2018), perhaps some species do perceive transverse sound. This possibility has not yet been explored.

Sonic philosophy (Wing 2020) deals with the metaphysics and phenomenology of auditory experiences. It attempts to answer the question: Do we hear sound (a process of wave propagation) or its source as a non-sound entity (a physical object or event)? Existence of transverse sound wave in addition to the longitudinal sound is expected to disrupt the discourse on the philosophy of sound.

Implications of Predicted Equivoluminal Waves: The wave theory of sound has been applied in such diverse fields as supersonic aerodynamics, thunder, blast, acoustic weapons, music, acoustic design, ultrasound imaging, hearing aids, SONAR, auditory perception of animals, sonic philosophy, etc. Auditory perception and sonic philosophy deal respectively with physiological/neurological and phenomenological aspects of hearing. These applications are based upon the presumption of the existence of only irrotational/longitudinal waves propagating through fluids. The presence of another slower sound wave as predicted here is expected to disrupt the foundations as well as the good design practice in all these application areas.

5. Sub-Elasticity and Hypoelasticity

The theory of hypoelasticity was proposed by Truesdell as a generalization of hyperelasticity and conventional Cauchy elasticity (Truesdell 1955a; Truesdell 1955b). Hypoelastic materials lack unique natural state and exhibit path-dependence of state of stress and strain energy in strain space. The hypoelastic constitutive equations are of rate-type expressing objective stress rate tensor as linear functions of rate of stretching tensor and the coefficients are determined by the instantaneous state of stress. Bernstein derived the hypoelastic equation for perfect fluids in terms of stress-deformation pairs. Noll established that if the state of stress in a hypoelastic material like an elastic fluid is ever hydrostatic, it must always be hydrostatic. Truesdell has established that the converse is also true (Truesdell 1963). Despite some later theoretical

developments (Xaio, Bruhns, and Meyers 1999), Maugin considers hypoelasticity theory to be doomed (Maugin 2016).

This simple rate-type hypoelastic constitutive equation $\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = \lambda D_{kk} \delta_{ij} + 2\mu D_{ij}$ is widely used, e. g., by Xaio, Bruhns, and Meyers, in finite deformation elastoplasticity models (Xaio, Bruhns, and Meyers 1999). As λ and μ are Lamé's constants are material constants, this represents the constitutive equation for the zero grade hypoelastic material. It is interesting to note that the proposed sub-elastic constitutive equations both for gases and liquids are of the same form. However, the Lamé-like coefficients in the rate-type sub-elastic constitutive equations for gases and liquids derived in first part of paper depend upon pressure apart from the adiabatic index for gases and bulk modulus of elasticity for liquids.

Hypoelasticity theory is formulated following a point-theoretic paradigm like elasticity theory, while sub-elasticity as the theory of partially elastic materials and structures is body-theoretic. Both hypoelastic and sub-elastic materials lack a unique natural state. The point-theoretic formulations cannot capture the configuration variation. As a matter of fact, the concepts of configuration and configuration variation have never been defined in the available literature on hypoelasticity. Still, many conclusions of hypoelasticity discussed above along with longitudinal and transverse hypoelastic waves (Bernstein 1962; Nariboli 1964) are compatible with sub-elasticity theory.

However, only body-theoretic sub-elastic theory, not point-theoretic hypoelasticity, can describe the behavior of mechanical systems like flexible cable structures, material bodied composed of cohesionless frictional materials, liquids, gases, etc. These mechanical systems have never been identified as hypoelastic materials. Also, sub-elastic materials and structures invariably belong to the class of homogeneous mechanical/dynamical systems. To be specific, the configuration-defining parameters, elastic displacements if any, and energy potentials are functions homogeneous of different orders of applied forces. Application of Euler's theorems for homogeneous functions yields new theorems applicable to sub-elastic systems. No such claim has ever been made in the context of hypoelasticity theory. In this sense, the more general sub-elasticity theory provides an avenue for grounding the conventional hypoelasticity theory.

Class of Sub-Elastic Systems: As shown above, the body dimensions of adiabatic gases are $\frac{-1}{(3\gamma-2)}$ order homogeneous function of equilibrated forces. The matrix in the universal equation $\frac{\dot{a}_i}{a_i} = N_{ij} \frac{\dot{P}_j}{P_j}$ turns out to be $N_{ij} = \frac{-(3\gamma-2)\delta_{ij}+(\gamma-1)}{3\gamma-2}$ with the eigenvalues $(-\frac{1}{3\gamma-2}, -1, -1)$.

To recapitulate, the present paper is motivated by the mechanical analogy between flexible sagging inextensible (elastic) cables and incompressible (elastic) liquid bodies. Similar analogy is shown to exist between the gravitational field and isothermal gaseous as well as elastic liquid bodies. The present author has interpreted the gravitational field as imparting stiffness to the gravitational sub-elastic nonlinear dynamical system composed of a moving point mass M in the gravitational field of an attracting point mass M_0 . As per Newton's law of universal gravitational attraction (1687), the force vector required to keep the mass M in equilibrium is given as $P_i = \frac{GM_0M}{r^3} x_i$. Its rate-type constitutive equations are stated as $\dot{P}_i = K_{ij}^t \dot{x}_j$ where $K_{ij}^t =$

$\frac{GM_0M}{r^5} [r^2 \delta_{ij} - 3x_i x_j]$. The eigenvalue analysis yields the eigenvalues as $\lambda_1 = -\frac{V_e^2 M}{r^2}$ and $\lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \frac{V_o^2 M}{r^2}$. The eigenvalues corresponding to the radial and circumferential mode are determined by escape velocity V_e and orbital velocity V_o respectively. The relation $c_1^2 = 2c_2^2$ between the speeds of longitudinal and transverse sound waves in isothermal gases mimics the known relation $V_e^2 = 2V_o^2$. The normalized universal gravitational equation is stated as $\frac{\dot{P}_i}{P_i} = Q_{ij} \frac{\dot{x}_j}{x_j}$ where $Q_{ij} = \delta_{ij} - 3n_j^2$ with n_i denoting the direction cosines of the radial vector of the attracted mass (Benipal 2025).

The gravitational sub-elastic nonlinear dynamical system obeys third order differential equation of motion $M\ddot{x}_i + K_{ij}^t \dot{x}_i = 0$. The eigenvalues of its tangent stiffness matrix K_{ij}^t being of mixed sense, it is expected to exhibit instantaneous both oscillatory and non-oscillatory modal response. To the best of author's knowledge, in this sense, the gravitational dynamical system is one of its kind.

Newton's law of gravitation can be restated as $x_i = \frac{GM_0M}{[P_1^2 + P_2^2 + P_3^2]^{3/4}} P_i$. The configuration-defining parameters turn out to be $(-\frac{1}{2})$ order homogeneous functions of the equilibrated forces. The The normalized universal gravitational equation is stated as $\frac{\dot{x}_i}{x_i} = N_{ij} \frac{\dot{P}_j}{P_j}$ where $N_{ij} = \delta_{ij} - \frac{3}{2}n_j^2$ with the eigenvalues as $(-\frac{1}{2}, +1, +1)$.

Consider a self-gravitating spherical body of radius R with constant density. The gravitational force acting at an infinitesimally small mass M at a point within the body is given by $P = Mg = M \frac{g_0}{R} r$ located at a radius r . Thus, one obtains the components of the force required to keep the mass in equilibrium as $P_i = \frac{GM_0M}{R^3} x_i$. The rate-type universal equation is stated as $\frac{\dot{P}_i}{P_i} = \delta_{ij} \frac{\dot{x}_j}{x_j}$. The eigenvalues of the universal matrix δ_{ij} are $(1, 1, 1)$ (Benipal 2025).

A point mass M tied at the end of a rigid bar of length L and under the action of axial tensile force T hinged at the other end constitutes another sub-elastic system. The components (P_1, P_2, P_3) of the force T determine the location (x_1, x_2, x_3) as $\frac{x_i}{L} = \frac{P_i}{T} = n_i$. The eigenvalues of the matrix $N_{ij} = \delta_{ij} - n_j^2$ in the normalised universal equation $\frac{\dot{x}_i}{x_i} = N_{ij} \frac{\dot{P}_j}{P_j}$ turn out to be $(0, 1, 1)$. The rate-type constitutive equation is obtained as $\dot{x}_i = f_{ij}^t \dot{P}_j$ where the tangent flexibility matrix $f_{ij}^t = \frac{L}{T} [\delta_{ij} - n_i n_j]$ is a singular matrix with eigenvalues $(0, \frac{L}{T}, \frac{L}{T})$. Here, the vanishing distinct eigenvalue corresponds to proportional loading and elastic mode, while the other two equal eigenvalues correspond to the circumferential mode with constant tensile force T . For the circular planar motion in the $x_1 - x_2$ plane requires that P_3 and n_3 vanish. In terms of the corresponding eigenvalue, the constitutive equation $\dot{P}_i = \frac{T}{L} \delta_{ij} \dot{x}_j$. The third order differential equation of motion $M\ddot{x}_i + \frac{T}{L} \dot{x}_i = 0$ can equivalently be stated as $\ddot{V}_i + \frac{T}{ML} V_i = 0$ in

terms of velocity vector. From structural dynamics, the natural frequency is obtained as $\omega = \sqrt{\frac{T}{ML}}$. This gives the well-known expression for ‘fictitious’ centrifugal force in circular motion as $T = ML\omega^2$. In the special case of constant gravitational force $P_2 = Mg = T$, the well-known expression for the period τ for small oscillations of the pendulum about the vertical direction is determined as $\tau = \frac{2\pi}{\omega} = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{L}{g}}$.

In contrast to the above rigid bar, consider an infinitely extensible bar obeying the constitutive equation $T = \alpha L$. In terms of the components of the force T , the rate-type universal equation is stated as $\frac{\dot{P}_i}{P_i} = \delta_{ij} \frac{\dot{x}_j}{x_j}$. The eigenvalues of the universal matrix δ_{ij} are obtained as (1, 1, 1).

The corresponding equation of state $q = \alpha V$ relates hydrostatic tension with volume.

Coulomb (1773) proposed the criterion for state of incipient shear failure at a plane for cohesionless frictional materials as $\tau = \mu\sigma$ in terms of shear and normal stresses. The corresponding criterion for incipient shear failure at a point was formulated by Mohr (1885) in terms of principal stresses ($\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_3$) as $\sigma_3 = \alpha\sigma_1$. Here, the coefficient of friction μ is related to the angle of internal friction ϕ , aka angle of repose, by the equation $\mu = \tan\phi$, while the coefficient $\alpha = \frac{1-\sin\phi}{1+\sin\phi}$. Also, compressive principal stresses are considered positive. Depending upon the magnitude of σ_2 , the following three cases of incipient shear failure are identified:

- I: $\sigma_1 > \sigma_2 > \sigma_3 > 0$ $\sigma_3 = \alpha\sigma_1$
 II: $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 > \sigma_3 > 0$ $\sigma_3 = \alpha\sigma_1 = \alpha\sigma_2$
 III: $\sigma_1 > \sigma_2 = \sigma_3 > 0$ $\sigma_3 = \sigma_2 = \alpha\sigma_1$

The dimensions of the rectangular parallelepipedon of volume $V = a_1 a_2 a_3 = \text{constant}$ for case III are obtained as follows for incompressible cohesionless frictional materials:

$$a_1 = \sqrt[3]{\frac{P_2}{\alpha P_1} \frac{P_3}{\alpha P_1} V} \quad a_2 = \sqrt[3]{\frac{P_3}{P_2} \frac{\alpha P_1}{P_2} V} \quad a_3 = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\alpha P_1}{P_3} \frac{P_2}{P_3} V}$$

The special case of cohesionless frictionless material ($\alpha = 1$) is indistinguishable from incompressible liquids. The material continues to be in the same state of incipient shear failure if the following loading criteria for different cases are satisfied: $\frac{\dot{P}_3}{P_3} < \frac{\dot{P}_1}{P_1}$ for case I and $\frac{\dot{P}_3}{P_3} < \frac{\dot{P}_1}{P_1}$ and $\frac{\dot{P}_3}{P_3} < \frac{\dot{P}_2}{P_2}$ for cases II and III. Here, positive values of \dot{P}_i imply increase in the magnitude of the force P_i . For all admissible values of ($0 < \alpha \leq 1$), the rate-type normalised universal equation $\dot{a}_i/a_i = A_{ij} \dot{P}_j/P_j$ as well as the eigenvalues of the universal matrix A_{ij} for cases II and III turn out to be same as those of incompressible liquids derived in the first part of the present paper. Cases I and II are analysed in a similar manner. Asymmetric constitutive matrix Y_{ij} in the constitutive equation $\dot{a}_i = Y_{ij} \dot{P}_j$ coupled with loading criteria results in dissipative plastic flow of cohesionless frictional materials (Benipal 1996; Benipal 2004).

Consider the class of purely configurational systems (with no elastic response) whose configuration-defining parameters are m order homogeneous function of equilibrated forces. The eigenvalues of the normalized universal configurational matrices for such sub-elastic systems are reproduced below:

Rigid pinned bar	$\lambda_1 = 0$	$\lambda_2 = +1$	$\lambda_3 = +1$
Incompressible cohesionless frictional materials	$\lambda_1 = 0$	$\lambda_2 = -1$	$\lambda_3 = -1$
Incompressible liquids	$\lambda_1 = 0$	$\lambda_2 = -1$	$\lambda_3 = -1$
Gravitational system: Mass outside the body	$\lambda_1 = -\frac{1}{2}$	$\lambda_2 = +1$	$\lambda_3 = +1$
Gravitational system: Mass within the body	$\lambda_1 = +1$	$\lambda_2 = +1$	$\lambda_3 = +1$
Infinitely extensible bar	$\lambda_1 = +1$	$\lambda_2 = +1$	$\lambda_3 = +1$
Isothermal gases	$\lambda_1 = -1$	$\lambda_2 = -1$	$\lambda_3 = -1$
Adiabatic gases	$\lambda_1 = -\frac{1}{3\gamma-2}$	$\lambda_2 = -1$	$\lambda_3 = -1$

A comparison of these universal eigenvalues of gravitational system with the attracted mass outside and within the body, rigid pinned bar, infinitely extensible bar, cohesionless frictional materials, gaseous bodies, and incompressible liquid bodies obtained in the present paper is instructive. Here, the sub-elastic mechanical systems are classified according to their distinct eigenvalues. In all these mechanical systems, at least two of the three eigenvalues are equal ($\lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \pm 1$) and correspond to pure distortion of configuration. Here, the distinct eigenvalue λ_1 corresponds to the change in size of the body under proportional loading. Also, the equality $\lambda_1 = m$ is invariably true. Its eigenvalues being $(m, \pm 1, \pm 1)$, the determinant ($\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3$) of the matrix N_{ij} always equals m .

The mass of the moving body is absent from the rate-type normalized universal constitutive equations. Except adiabatic gases, even the material parameters are absent from their universal eigenvalues. There is an inverse relationship between the eigenvalues of the ‘outside’ gravitational system and the elastic liquid and among the eigenvalues of the ‘inside’ gravitational system, infinitely extensible bar, and the isothermal gas. The eigenvalues of incompressible liquids and cohesionless frictional materials turn out to be same. These relations between the eigenvalues of these systems suggest the underlying unity of mechanical response of these sub-elastic mechanical systems distinct from the conventional elastic or viscous systems.

From a historical perspective, the sub-elastic systems turn out to be pre-elastic, i.e., predating Cauchy’s theory (1822) of fully elastically constrained elastic solids with specified configuration. The foundations of fluid mechanics and acoustics were laid by Newton, Daniel Bernoulli, Johann Bernoulli, D’Alembert, Euler, and some others during the Enlightenment period in the long eighteenth century starting from Newton (1687) till Navier, Cauchy, Laplace, and Poisson (1825).

Non-Polar Elastic Solids as Sub-Elastic Materials: To recapitulate, Kepler's laws of planetary motion predict their translational motion but are silent about their rotational motion. Also, Newton's laws of motion and of universal gravitation pertain only to forces and translational motion. Theories of non-polar elastic and viscous materials too are stated in terms of Cauchy's force stress tensor and linear displacement and velocity vectors. Euler's laws of rotational motion of rigid bodies imply symmetry of Cauchy stress tensor. Brothers E & F Cosserat (1909) proposed a theory of polar elastic solids which can resist asymmetric Cauchy stress tensor along with couple stresses. The couple stresses are determined by elastic flexural and torsional curvatures (Truesdell and Toupin 1960). As the elastic lines and surfaces are endowed with flexural and torsional rigidities, these bodies can be classified as polar elastic systems. Despite this fact, the external loads associated with gravitation, air/winds, water/currents, and granular materials are invariably applied to these structures as forces, but not moments.

Now, non-polar elastic solids cannot mobilize elastic resistance to anti-symmetric part of Cauchy stress tensor and couple stresses. As such, non-polar elastic solids belong to the class of sub-elastic mechanical systems. Perhaps, Truesdell's theory of hypoelasticity can be interpreted as a sub-elastic theory of non-polar elastic solids. In the hypoelastic constitutive equation, the Zaremba-Jaumann objective stress rate tensor $\tilde{\sigma}$ is given by $\tilde{\sigma} = \dot{\sigma} + \sigma W - W\sigma$ where $\dot{\sigma}$ represents Cauchy stress rate tensor. Here, $\tilde{\sigma}$ is determined by both the rate of stretching tensor D as well as the spin tensor W while $\dot{\sigma}$ is determined only by D (Malvern 1969). The configurational resistance to spin-dependent part of objective stress rate tensor depends upon the current Cauchy stress tensor, but not any elastic constant. In a state of rest, the elastic strain tensor, not rotation tensor, determine the total Cauchy stress tensor σ in hypoelastic materials. However, in the hypoelastic formulation, there is no reference to anti-symmetric part of stress rate tensor, variable configuration and homogeneous functions.

An attempt has been made by the author (Benipal 2004) to construct a rudimentary sub-elasticity theory of non-polar elastic solids. Recall that in finite elasticity, principal stress axes also play the role of acoustic axes. One longitudinal and two transverse waves travel along each principal stress axis (Truesdell and Noll 1965). The elasticity axes and acoustic axes in bimodular solids too are oriented along principal stress/strain directions (Raveendra Babu, Singh, and Benipal 2010). In photoelasticity, isoclinics indicate the principal stress directions, while isochromatics represent the difference between the principal stresses. Further, according to Wolff's law (1872) of bone remodelling under sustained or repeated loading, the principal elasticity axes of cancellous bones eventually get oriented along the principal stress directions (Benipal 1997).

In author's formulation, the network of mutually orthogonal three principal stress directions or of three mutually orthogonal surfaces defines the configuration of non-polar elastic bodies. These lines and surfaces are perfectly flexible and twistable lines and surfaces resembling abstract cables and membranes. This reference to flexible cables is not a fortuitous coincidence but reveals the fundamental sub-elastic unification. Just mentioning string theory and brane cosmology along with sub-elastic approach to flexible lines and membranes is a great ego booster.

As per Cauchy's theory of homogeneous isotropic linear non-polar solids, the principal stresses and the orientation of principal stress axes at any point are functions homogeneous of order one and zero of the Cauchy stress tensor components at that point. Thus, proportional variation

of stress tensor components results in linear variation of principal stresses but does not affect the orientation of principal stress directions. Non-proportional variations also cause the principal stress axes to rotate and so cause the configuration to change. In contrast to the elastic rotations measure relative to absolute space, the rotation of principal stress axes occurs relative to the material space. In its passive or natural state, the non-polar solid body lacks unique configuration, but definite equilibrium state configuration.

It is conjectured that continuous variation of applied forces on the body introduces stress rates including admissible symmetric force stress rate tensor and the inadmissible anti-symmetric force stress rate tensor and the balancing couple stress rate tensor. Even though the shear stresses vanish on principal planes (orthogonal to principal stress axes), the shear stress rates on these principal planes are generally non-zero. When a non-polar elastic solid body supporting admissible stress field is subjected to an addition external loading, the body in motion responds by orienting its principal stress axes such that the inadmissible stress field vanishes. In the new equilibrium state configuration, the material body supports only admissible stress field.

Truesdell and Noll have observed that the equilibrium state of an elastic solid is stable under superposed incremental rotation about the one of the principal stress axes, say N_3 , if the sum of the other two principal stresses, $\sigma_1 + \sigma_2$, is positive (Truesdell and Noll 1965). Perhaps, this is why fluids, being under hydrostatic pressure, cannot mobilize any resistance to vortex motion resulting in well-known vorticity and circulation theorems.

6. Philosophical Perspectives

Development of a genuinely new physical theory like the one presented here gives rise to many foundational and philosophical issues. Some of these issues are discussed below:

Motivation, Creativity, and Methodology: Though the existence of transverse sound waves is predicted in this paper, it was not its intended objective. Anyway, no research investigation can be undertaken with the objective of proving the existence of currently inadmissible transverse wave. In a moment of epiphany, it dawned upon the present author that the flexible sagging cables, cohesionless frictional materials, and liquids as sub-elastic systems belong to the same class of homogeneous mechanical systems. The rectangular parallelepipedon as material body subjected to normal forces was chosen to capture configuration variation with applied forces as in the case of sagging cables. The primary motivation came from author's intention to understand the mechanics of liquids and gases as sub-elastic materials. In the absence of this explanation for its motivation, the present investigation undertaken to achieve the explicitly stated objective of proving the existence of 'inadmissible' transverse sound would look like magic or eastern mysticism. The foundational significance of proposed sub-elastic wave theory of sound can be appreciated only after deconstructing the Euler theory of inviscid fluids, Laplace correction of Newton's formula, and Poisson's wave theory of sound.

In the process of implementing this intention, constitutive equations, equations of motion, hyperbolic wave equations, and formulae for speed of sound waves got developed. This

creative process followed the existing template of theory of cables (Kumar, Ganguli, and Benipal 2016), supported by the classical theories of elasticity, structural dynamics, and elastic wave propagation. The natural internal logic of the investigation coupled with creative imagination resulted in a new sub-elastic wave theory of sound. As for the epistemological aspects of the investigation, here the rational conception of transverse sound takes precedence over its perceptual experience and experimental detection. In other words, the transverse sound is not presented here as a discovery, but as an invention.

From the creative experiences of many established mathematicians and scientists, Hadamard has made a case for the role of subconscious mental processes in the mathematical invention and creativity (Hadamard 1996). Chandrasekhar has attempted to delineate the role played by the concept of beauty in the truth of scientific imagination. The simplicity of Einstein's equation $E = mc^2$ and Euler's formula $e^{i\pi} = -1$ are considered to exemplify the relation between beauty and truth (Chandrasekhar 1987). In the present investigation, the simplicity of the formulae for speed of sub-elastic sound waves and small integer values of universal configurational matrices for diverse sub-elastic systems seem to represent a similar sense of aesthetics.

Rational methodology without any empirical fudge factors is adopted for construction of the present theory. An attempt has been made here to capture the rational spirit in modern continuum mechanics (Man and Fosdick 2004). No claim is made for better empirical predictions, and no experiments are conducted to validate theoretical predictions. The proposed sub-elastic wave theory of sound shares its empirical basis with the existing wave theory. To be specific, the proposed theory is deduced from the well-known empirical equations of state for gases and liquids. These equations of state were earlier formulated by induction from substantial experimental data. The mathematical deduction is carried out without using Euler's equations for inviscid fluids, continuity equation, Laplace thermodynamic formula for speed of sound, and Poisson's wave theory of sound. The proposed theory is purely analytical plus mechanical intuition sans experimentation, computation, and even advanced mathematics.

Chandrasekhar's Fluid Dynamics: Apart from making substantial contributions to astrophysics and relativity, Indian Nobel Laureate S. Chandrasekhar worked on hydrodynamic stability and turbulence in which he had no formal instruction. The normal method of conducting research in fluid mechanics chosen by him involved working on diverse specific analytical, empirical, and numerical problems, not conducting foundations research suiting his style of research. This is why Chandrasekhar could not make any fundamental contributions to fluid dynamics, got tired of the subject, and sought refuge in relativity (Sreenivasan 2019). Einstein's theory of relativity is premised upon the Light Postulate. Cheng and Read have explored the possibility of constructing a similar theory of 'sonic relativity' based upon the 'Sound Postulate' (Cheng and Read 2021).

Confirmation of the Proposed Theory: Derivation of Laplace formula for the speed of arial sound and Colladon - Sturm formula for speed of sound through liquids in the limiting case of vanishing pressure partially confirms the basic soundness of the proposed theory. The general formula derived here predicts that speed of sound through liquids increases with pressure. This prediction is qualitatively compatible with the observed increase, with pressure, of speed of

sound through water (Bollengier, Brown, and Shaw 2019) and through liquid Triolein (Kielczynski, Szalewski, and Piekarski 2013).

Problems of Bodies and Motion: Problem of Bodies has been identified by Brading and Stan as the central problem of philosophy of classical mechanics in the eighteenth century. Search for solution of this problem animated both philosophy and physics, and the interaction between the two disciplines (Brading and Stan 2024). Here, in place of Newton's mass points, Euler's rigid bodies, and Euler-Cauchy's material points, rectangular parallelepipedon is chosen as the body of reference. It is argued by Stan that the doctrines of body and motion proposed by Newton, Leibniz, and Kant are insufficient. More important contributions are credited to Bernoulli, Euler, Cauchy, Navier, and Stokes (Stan 2023). According to Stan, the Euler-Cauchy dynamical laws of motion demonstrate that it is not the force *a la* Newton, but the divergence of stress tensor which causes acceleration (Stan 2022). In the present paper, the rate-type version of Cauchy's dynamical equations of motion stated in terms of stress rates and rate of acceleration are employed as proper governing equations of motion of sub-elastic gases and liquids. This has resulted in Navier-like nonlinear third order differential equation of motion for sub-elastic dynamical systems. It has been argued by the author that third order differential equation of motion is the proper equation of motion for MDOF nonlinear structures. This is because of the fact that, for such structures, it is not possible to establish the unique secant stiffness matrix K_{ij}^s while the tangent stiffness matrix K_{ij}^t is always unique. However, for m order homogeneous mechanical systems, as $mK_{ij}^s = K_{ij}^t$, the equivalent second order differential equation of motion can also be used. In fact, for first order homogeneous inherently nonlinear mechanical systems, the tangent and secant stiffness matrices are identical ($K_{ij}^s = K_{ij}^t$) (Benipal 2019).

Falsifiability Criterion: As demanded by Popper's falsifiability criterion (Popper 1959), the theory of sound proposed here predicts the existence of new equivoluminal sound waves propagating through gases and liquids at definite speeds. However, absence of experimental results confirming the existence of transverse sound does not constitute the refutation of the claims of its existence. Still, experiments conducted to measure the speed of transverse sound can refute the proposed theory by demonstrating the incompatibility between the observed and predicted speeds.

Scientific Change: To recapitulate, there is a consensus in the acoustics community that fluids can support the propagation of irrotational waves only. The equivoluminal sound waves predicted in the present paper are deemed inadmissible. Till these waves are detected, their ontological status remains suspect. Derivation of correct formulae for speed of irrotational sound wave can be considered to partly confirm the basic soundness of the proposed theory. In that case, the existence of equivoluminal sound wave predicted by the same theory must be accepted. Otherwise, some error must be detected in the theory. If no error is detected in the derivation, then the denial of existence of equivoluminal sound wave must be justified on some other grounds. Peer acceptance of the predicted transverse sound waves would constitute an example of scientific change in acoustics.

Diverse Rationalities: It must be noted that, in this paper, Euler's theory of inviscid fluids and Poisson's wave theory of sound have not been explicitly proved to be wrong. Thus, the proposed sub-elasticity approach yields other equally rational yet different theories of inviscid fluids and acoustics. Starting from the equivalent equations of state of gases and liquids, the same speeds of longitudinal sound waves are predicted here as by Poisson's wave theory. In other words, the same empirical data on longitudinal waves confirms two distinct rational wave theories. Experimental data and even successful technological applications of a scientific theory do not confirm the realism of its concepts and basic hypotheses. Whether equally rational alternative scientific theories compatible with the same empirical observations are admissible or not is a matter belonging to the philosophy of science.

Here, the possibility of diverse rationalities of science is deemed admissible. Different point-theoretic and body-theoretic perspectives reveal different sceneries. A change of scenery when viewed from a different perspective constitutes a mode of scientific change. Such an understanding of scientific change guards against the perils of arrogant scientism based upon the notion of scientific progress. As argued by Dellsen (Dellsen 2016), the positivists' idea of linear scientific progress must be discarded in favor of value-free scientific change.

It is commonly believed that both empiricism and rationalism are required to construct new theories. However, it is argued by philosophers of science that it is possible to make substantial progress by rationalism alone. It is further claimed by Darrigol that fundamental laws of classical mechanics derived from specified space-time structure and particular characterization of mechanical systems are necessarily true (Darrigol 2007; Darrigol 2014). The possibility of diverse rationalities mentioned above challenges such beliefs about uniqueness of dominant rational theories of classical mechanics.

It is claimed that the scientific theories precipitating paradigm-shift are incomprehensible to those steeped in old paradigm. In contrast, the new theories of sub-elastic theories of fluid mechanics and acoustics proposed here can be easily understood by everybody conversant with earlier theories.

The new theory proposed here along with other new theories (Birkhoff 1950; Brenner 2003; Ivanov and Ivanova 2015; Liu and Liu 2021; Kirtskhalia 2022; Taha, Gonzales, and Shorbagy 2023) are examples of equally rational contending theories. This critical turn in fluid mechanics needs to be examined as has been attempted in engineering sciences by the author (Benipal 1997; Benipal 2015). After all, within a decade after its endorsement by Rayleigh (1877), an attempt was made by Mott to refute, though unsuccessfully, even the then currently dominant wave theory of sound (Mott 1885). In the eighteenth century, Euler was recognized as the genius who turned 'the establishment' into profit (Truesdell 1984). It turns out that, in later centuries, Euler himself transformed into a powerful establishment in fluid mechanics hindering further progress in this field. Cold peer reception to new theories in fluid mechanics constitutes the evidence justifying above contention.

It has been observed that, during the last century, the field of viscous and compressible complex flow is dominated by computational and experimental methods and theoretical fluid dynamics publications are apparently missing from contemporary literature. Wu, Liu, and Liu explain

that these computational and experimental methods themselves are premised upon the classical fundamental theories developed earlier (Wu, Liu, and Liu, 2018).

An investigation into the matter of refused knowledge in the present era of epistemic pluralism is hoped by Neresini, Crabu, Agodi, and Tosoni to also contribute to Science and Technology Studies (Neresini et al 2024). Earlier title for the present paper was “Another Rational Theory of Sound” but the existing well-known theories of fluid mechanics and acoustics are not branded false or irrational. Even incomplete or partly wrong theories can turn out to be valuable. While reviewing Zuber’s 1958 doctoral dissertation under Tribus, Lienhard and White (Lienhard and White 1985) observed: *‘This dissertation, titled Hydrodynamic Aspects of Boiling, was an audacious and far-ranging study that awakened passionate and heated opposition. It was a work which, while not correct in all its details, ranks among the small handful of true milestones in this staggering profusion of writings.’* Even in the eventuality of the proposed sub-elasticity theory being judged to be wrong in many respects, the residual question shall remain to be answered: Why does such a wrong theory of sound predict correctly the speed of propagation of irrotational waves through gases and liquids?

As exhorted by Popper (Popper 1959), the present Author is eagerly looking forward to any criticism of the proposed theory. However, as experience testifies, the peer response to new theories challenging established theories generally lacks enthusiasm and active engagement. This is because the researchers involved in experimentation, applications, sponsored research, numerical methods, computational mechanics like CFD, molecular dynamics, 3-D printing, and AI/ML techniques repose infinite belief in the basic soundness and completeness of the classical theories. Consequently, there is a general lack of interest among researchers in the foundations of their disciplines.

7. Prospects for Further Research

To recapitulate, the proposed theory is constructed using many physical and mathematical hypotheses without providing their convincing rigorous justification. It is expected that at the hands of competent mathematicians, mechanicians, and acousticians, the proposed theory can be transformed into a rigorous formal axiomatic theory with new theorems. First, the finite-sized rectangular parallelepipedon needs to be replaced by a differential element in the form of a rectangular parallelepipedon. The scope of the present paper is restricted to barotropic gases and liquids neglecting the role played by variable temperature and thermodynamics. It is well-known that the isothermal and adiabatic equations of state correspond to the limiting cases of gases with infinitely high and infinitely low thermal conductivity respectively. Sub-elastic theory of acoustic wave propagation proposed here is not valid for real gases possess definite thermal conductivity.

The proper status of continuity equation fluid mechanics is rendered suspect. The status of Euler’s equations of motion vis-à-vis the proposed dynamical equations of motion needs more clarification. Similarly, comparative evaluation of Poisson’s wave theory and the sub-elastic wave theory proposed herein must be undertaken. The theory of sound proposed herein also is derived using only the local acceleration in place of the more appropriate convective

acceleration. The perturbations of the velocity field are assumed to be small. Indeed, more rigorous theories of gases and liquids free from these simplifications need to be constructed.

Theories of polar elasticity, liquid crystals, and polar hypoplasticity of cohesionless frictional materials have already been developed. Even a theory of gravitation, called gravitomagnetism, predicting gravitational rotation of a small body located near a massive rotating body has been proposed. However, the sub-elasticity theories of non-polar gases, liquids, cohesionless frictional materials, elastic solids, and gravitation are yet to be developed. Like the configurational stiffness matrix defined here, the statical-kinematic stiffness matrix of underconstrained systems depends upon the configuration and the equilibrated forces (Kuznetsov 1997). This suggests the essentially sub-elastic nature of the under-constrained systems.

No experimental data is available for validating the existence of transverse waves predicted here. The required experimental investigations need to be undertaken on both gases and liquids. It is suggested that, because of its elastic deformations being equivoluminal, small vibrating rubber body may be used to generate equivoluminal/transverse waves in large gaseous and liquid bodies. Also, a set of two similar stretched strings vibrating out of phase in orthogonal planes are expected to generate transverse waves.

The proposed theory of inviscid gases and liquids can also be extended to viscous fluids. Taking seriously the new theories may result in reformulation of governing equations of fluid mechanics and so in the resolution of paradoxes and the dissolution of the Millennium Prize Problem. Then and only then, theoretical fluid mechanics shall attain the status of the complete rigorous living theory of rational continuum mechanics.

Having identified the Newtonian gravitational dynamical system as a sub-elastic system, it is a dream project of the author to provide a sub-elastic reformulation of Newton's laws of translatory motion of mass points and Euler's laws of motion of rigid bodies. It will be helpful to consider the motion of a point mass subjected to at least four conservative concurrent forces. The magnitude and direction cosines of their resultant force and the corresponding resulting translational acceleration by Newton's second law are functions homogeneous respectively of order one and zero of the applied forces. Newton's first law of motion may be reformulated as follows: A point mass continues to move at uniform velocity under proportional variations of concurrent mutually equilibrated forces. Non-proportional variation of such forces results in net resultant force causing motion according to Newton's second law of motion. Similarly, Euler's laws can be reformulated by considering a rigid body under the action of certain minimum number of applied forces and moments. As per author's Strong Program in Sub-Elasticity, here called Meta-Elasticity Program, the entire field of classical mechanics can be reformulated from sub-elasticity perspective.

Due to Earth's rotation about its own axis, a point located on its surface at the equator moves at a linear speed of 1669 km/h. The maximum wind speed relative to the Earth's surface is 407 km/h observed till date and the theoretically maximum wind speed equals the thermal motion of molecules given as 443 km/h. The speed of arial sound relative to wind near the Earth's surface is 1235 km/h. This implies that the maximum speed of sound relative to Earth's surface

1678 km/h. It is conjectured that the acoustic signals cannot be transmitted through Earth's atmosphere faster than the speed of any point at equator due to Earth's rotation. Due to its synchronous rotation, the Moon barely rotates about its own axis. Also, the Moon lacks atmosphere, sound wave propagation, and the wind. Thus, it too seems to obey, though merely vacuously, the above conjecture. A natural philosophy perspective is needed to unravel these intriguing coincidences relating the astronomical and atmospheric phenomena.

Since it was included in the list of Millennium Prize Problems posed by the Clay Mathematical Institute in 2000 CE, the existence and smoothness of the solutions of the Navier-Stokes Equations have been explored by many researchers. Sophisticated mathematical and numerical methods and techniques have been brought to bear upon the problem. Still, it has not been possible to solve the problem. According to Fefferman, the standard theory of partial differential equations appears to be inadequate for this purpose. There is a need for new deep perspectives (Fefferman 2006). Some mathematicians seem to have abandoned the analytical route to solve the Navier-Stokes Problem. Terence Tao has recently proposed the construction of a "Liquid Computer" for solving it (Tao 2014; Tao 2025). Perhaps, the mathematicians have devoted considerable mathematical ingenuity on an ill-posed problem.

8. Conclusions

In the preceding part of the paper, author's sub-elasticity theory is presented along with its applications to gas mechanics, liquid mechanics, and acoustics. Alternative equivalent versions of equations of state are developed and interpreted as constitutive equations. Equations of motion and wave equations stated in terms of velocity vector field are derived. Starting from their equations of state, Euler's unified theory of inviscid fluids is replaced by dedicated theories of gases and liquids. Sub-elastic wave theory of sound replacing Poisson's wave theory is proposed without invoking Laplace general formula for speed of longitudinal sound, continuity equation, and Euler's equations of motion. Apart from acceptable formulae for the longitudinal sound waves, the transverse sound waves are predicted to propagate through gases and liquids.

The creation and significance of the sub-elastic wave theory of sound for classical fluid mechanics, classical theory of sound, hypoelasticity, and philosophy of science are discussed in this second part of the paper.

First, the new concepts and hypotheses underlying the proposed neo-classical sub-elastic theories of fluid mechanics and acoustics are stated explicitly. To recapitulate, new concepts and hypotheses include finite-size rectangular parallelepipedon as body of reference, full rate-of-(Cauchy) stress-tensor, motion-dependent pressure, Cauchy-like equation of motion, rate-type constitutive equations, Navier-like equations of motion involving jerk, and propagation of transverse sound. Some preliminary explanation for their choice is provided along with the derivation. It is realized that a closer scrutiny of the mathematical and mechanical foundations of the proposed theory is required. It is hoped that such scrutiny will result in mature formal axiomatic sub-elastic theories.

Euler's unified theory of gases and liquids is based on the concept of pressure. Here, this concept of fluid pressure is critically evaluated and a new principle of determinism of pressure by velocity is proposed. Thus, the proposed sub-elastic theory of gases and liquids is a generalization of Euler's theory of fluids based on motion-independence of pressure. The steady flow of indefinite is deemed to lead to instability. The stress rate tensor components pertain to rates of full Cauchy stress tensor. New Navier-like equations of motion demand different boundary conditions and initial conditions for formulating initial/boundary value problems.

A new Principle of equivalence among inertial, gravitational, and pressure fields is proposed. A new relation between fluid pressure and density is derived from Euler's equations of motion and Gauss' divergence theorem for gravitational field. The matter of measurement and causality in fluid mechanics is raised. Expressions for sub-elastic configurational energy for gases and liquids are derived and compared with the pressure potential appearing in Bernoulli's theorem. It is conjectured that during fluid flow, the gravitational acceleration constitutes an upper limit of fluid acceleration. The classical afflux problem is reinterpreted in terms of Variable Mass Dynamics.

Poisson's wave theory of sound is based upon algebraic concepts like acoustic pressure and condensation as pressure and density perturbations. In contrast, the constitutive equations of the sub-elastic wave theory are rate-type. In place of scalar pressure longitudinal wave, sub-elastic longitudinal and transverse waves as perturbations in the velocity vector field are predicted to propagate through gases and liquids. The continuity equation is absent from the new formulation. The qualitative effect of pressure on the speed of longitudinal waves through liquids is compatible with experimental observations. Absence of detection or perception of transverse waves is explained. In the absence of direct evidence, some indirect evidence for the existence of transverse waves in the form of gravity waves, evanescent wave coupling, hypoelastic waves, and shear waves in viscous fluids is presented. The aerodynamic drag-divergence Mach number approximately corresponds the Mach number of the transverse waves. So does the Mach number corresponding to the commencement of subsonic turbulence in air.

It is argued that the flow-induced stiffness in fluids can cause the flow-induced sound. Unified inhomogeneous wave equations with source terms are derived for liquids and incompressible flows of gases. The velocity of liquids through an orifice in a container is shown to be twice the speed of transverse sound, while the corresponding relation for gases is more complex. There are many implications of the predicted transverse sound for various applications in physics, engineering, sound perception, and sonic philosophy.

Both point-theoretic hypoelasticity theory and the body-theoretic sub-elasticity theory proposed herein claim to deal with materials without unique natural state and obey rate-type constitutive equations. However, the sub-elasticity theory is more general as it deals with mechanical systems like sub-elastic materials and structures composed of them. Also, in contrast to hypoelasticity theory, theory of homogeneous functions is identified as the mathematical foundation of the sub-elasticity theory. Some purely configurational systems like gases, incompressible liquids and cohesionless frictional materials, inextensible and infinitely

extensible bars, and gravitational fields are identified as sub-elastic mechanical systems. For such systems, normalized universal rate-type constitutive equations $\frac{\dot{a}_i}{a_i} = N_{ij} \frac{\dot{p}_j}{p_j}$ are proposed. A comparison of the eigenvalues of their universal matrices N_{ij} reveals their essential sub-elastic nature. These equations are universal laws of configuration change for purely configurational sub-elastic systems.

The philosophical aspects like motivation, creativity, testability, diverse rationalities, etc., of the proposed theory are discussed. To recapitulate, the Cable-Liquid Analogy perceived by the author provided sufficient motivation for exploring the mechanics of liquids and gases as sub-elastic states of matter. This intention led to the construction of sub-elastic theories of gases, liquids, and acoustics. The transverse sound wave is an invention rather than a discovery. The proposed sub-elastic theory shares the empirical foundations of the classical theories of fluids and acoustics. Here, these classical theories are not claimed to be false, but rather equally rational different theories thus admitting the possibility of diverse rationalities. Thus, the notion of scientific change, rather than scientific progress, is confirmed here. The proposed theory is characterized by the choice of rectangular parallelepipedon as an object of study and kinetic equations of motion. Testable predictions are made here for empirical validation of the theory.

Prospects for further research include the generation and detection of transverse sound, construction of thermodynamically consistent sub-elastic theory of gases, extension of the proposed theory to viscous fluids, construction of sub-elastic theories of non-polar solids, liquids, gases, and gravitation, sub-elastic reformulation of Newton-Euler laws of motion, etc. Such attempts will exemplify the value of the natural philosophy perspective in physical sciences.

Finally, the proposed theory along with other new theories of fluids and acoustics listed above must be evaluated critically as partly correct or even failed theories are valuable. It is hoped that the present theory will provoke some interest in the foundations of sub-elasticity theory, fluid mechanics and acoustics, and in general classical mechanics.

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